

Output current ripple analysis of single phase inverter with discontinuous PWM

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Sep 29, 2023

Revised May 2, 2024

Accepted May 22, 2024

Keywords:

DPWM

Modulation index

Output current ripple

Single phase inverter

SPWM

ABSTRACT

Voltage source inverter has been applied for uninterruptible power supply (UPS), renewable energy sources, and motor drive. The popular modulations for inverters are sinusoidal pulse width modulation (SPWM), zero sequence signal modulation (ZSS), space vector modulation (SVM), and discontinuous PWM (DPWM). All these modulations have been applied to three-phase and multiphase inverters. The characteristics of the modulation application in these inverters have been well investigated. However, only SPWM has been applied satisfactorily in single-phase inverter. From the literature, the applications of ZSS and DPWM couldn't show any benefit. In this paper, a DPWM is proposed for single-phase inverter. The output current ripple is analyzed and experiments are conducted to verify the analytical result. Comparison to SPWM is conducted to find the modulation index range that provides a benefit when using the DPWM.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Single-phase inverters have been applied in motor drives, UPS, and renewable energy sources [1]-[7]. Much literature has been published related to single-phase inverter. Among them can be categorized into inverter topology, control algorithm, and modulation technique [4]-[13]. Many inverter topologies have been proposed e.g. half/full bridge inverter, multilevel inverter, H5/H6 inverter, T-type inverter, HERIC inverter, and differential inverter [4]-[6], [12]-[15]. Single-phase full bridge inverter gives high efficiency and high-reliability characteristics. However, it needs a large DC link capacitor to absorb the ripples through it i.e. high frequency voltage/current ripple and low frequency 2ω ripple.

The SPWM for a single-phase full bridge inverter can be divided into bipolar and unipolar modulations. A single-phase full-bridge inverter has two legs of switching components. In bipolar modulation, one reference is used for the two legs. The two legs get opposite commands. Unipolar modulation uses two references that are 180° out of phase for both legs. This modulation can be divided into two types i.e. asymmetrical and symmetrical modulations. Asymmetrical modulation allows one leg to be switched with high frequency and the other leg to be switched with fundamental frequency. Thus, the losses in the two legs are not balanced. Whereas in symmetrical modulation, both legs are switched at the same frequency. Symmetrical unipolar modulation provides the smallest output current ripple compared to asymmetrical unipolar and bipolar modulations [16].

Besides SPWM, other types of modulations that can be found in the literature are ZSS, SVM, and DPWM. These modulation types have been applied successfully in three-phase and multiphase inverters

[17]-[24]. However, the successful application in single-phase inverters is still rarely reported in literature. The application of ZSS in a single-phase inverter cannot increase the linear modulation range [25]. Several DPWMs also have been proposed [25]-[29]. However, the proposed DPWMs in [27], [28] produce low-order harmonics. In this paper, a DPWM is proposed which has the advantage of being simple and does not produce low-order harmonics. The output current ripple is derived and experimental results are also presented. The output current ripple of the DPWM is compared to SPWM to find out the modulation index range which can provide an advantage when using DPWM.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Output current ripple analysis

The single-phase full bridge inverter is shown in Figure 1(a). A single-phase full-bridge inverter converts a DC voltage to an AC voltage by using a modulation technique to the bridge circuit. The bridge circuit is made of semiconductor switching devices e.g. MOSFET or IGBT. Then, a filter is used to produce sinusoidal current and voltage. The reference signals of the proposed DPWM for legs A and B are shown in Figure 1(b). As we can see, the waveform pattern is repeated every $\pi/2$ interval. The equations of the reference signals are shown in Table 1. These reference signals are sinusoidal signals with signal injection as shown in the table. At the angle values less than gamma (we call here a discontinuous angle), sinusoidal references are used. At the angle values above gamma, a discontinuous reference is introduced.

The reference signal is compared to a carrier signal to produce the ON-OFF signal for the inverter leg. If the reference signal is higher than the carrier signal, an ON signal is produced. This means the upper switching component is switched and the lower switching component is left to be open. The OFF signal is produced when the reference signal is lower than the carrier signal. In this situation, it is the lower switching component that is to be switched and the upper switching device is left to be open. The waveforms during a switching period T_s are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), each for angles less than gamma and more than gamma, respectively.

Figure 1. Single phase full bridge inverter: (a) circuit and (b) DPWM reference signals

Table 1. DPWM reference signals

Interval	Signal Injection	v_A^r	v_B^r
$0 \leq \theta < \gamma$	0	$k \sin(\theta)$	$-k \sin(\theta)$
$\gamma \leq \theta < \pi/2$	$-1 + k \sin(\theta)$	$2k \sin(\theta) - 1$	-1
$\pi/2 \leq \theta < \pi - \gamma$	$1 - k \sin(\theta)$	1	$1 - 2k \sin(\theta)$
$\pi - \gamma \leq \theta < \pi$	0	$k \sin(\theta)$	$-k \sin(\theta)$
$\pi \leq \theta < \pi + \gamma$	0	$k \sin(\theta)$	$-k \sin(\theta)$
$\pi + \gamma \leq \theta < 3\pi/2$	$1 + k \sin(\theta)$	$2k \sin(\theta) + 1$	1
$3\pi/2 \leq \theta < 2\pi - \gamma$	$-1 - k \sin(\theta)$	-1	$-1 - 2k \sin(\theta)$
$2\pi - \gamma \leq \theta < 2\pi$	0	$k \sin(\theta)$	$-k \sin(\theta)$

To analyze the output current ripple, firstly the mean square value of the current ripple during the switching period is formulated. After that, the mean square value during a fundamental period is calculated. The switching period is determined by the frequency of the carrier signal and the fundamental period by the reference signal. The carrier frequency is much higher than the reference signals. As a result, the reference signals are assumed to be constant during the switching period.

Figure 2. The waveforms during a switching period (a) interval of $0 \leq \theta < \gamma$ and (b) interval of $\gamma \leq \theta < \pi/2$

From Figure 1(a), the inverter output voltage can be represented as (1).

$$v_{AB} = Ri_o + L \frac{di_o}{dt} + e \tag{1}$$

Because of the switching action, the voltage and the current consist of their average and the ripple components. The (1) can be written as (2).

$$\bar{v}_{AB} + \tilde{v}_{AB} = R(\bar{i}_o + \tilde{i}_o) + L \frac{d(\bar{i}_o + \tilde{i}_o)}{dt} + e \tag{2}$$

The above equation can be separated into the average (3) and the ripple (4), i.e.

$$\bar{v}_{AB} = R\bar{i}_o + L \frac{d\bar{i}_o}{dt} + e \tag{3}$$

$$\tilde{v}_{AB} = R\tilde{i}_o + L \frac{d\tilde{i}_o}{dt} \tag{4}$$

The ripple voltage drop across the resistance R is much smaller than the one across the inductor. So, from (4) the expression for the output current ripple can be represented as (5).

$$\tilde{i}_o \approx \frac{1}{L} \int (v_{AB} - \bar{v}_{AB}) dt \tag{5}$$

The average value of the output voltage is in (6).

$$\bar{v}_{AB} = E_d k \sin(\theta) \tag{6}$$

In (1) to (6) v_{AB} is the voltage between points A and B, R is the load resistance, L is the load inductance, i_o is the output current, e is the back electromotive force, $\bar{\cdot}$ is the average value, $\tilde{\cdot}$ is the ripple value, E_d is the DC input voltage, k is the modulation index, $\theta = 2\pi f_o t$ is the angle, f_o is the fundamental frequency, and t is the time.

Based on Figure 2(a), the current ripple in the interval of $0 \leq \theta < \gamma$ can be represented as (7).

$$\tilde{i}_{o1} = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_0) & , t_0 \leq t \leq t_1 \\ \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_1) + \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)T_0 & , t_1 \leq t \leq t_2 \\ \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_3) & , t_2 \leq t \leq t_4 \\ \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_4) + \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)T_2 & , t_4 \leq t \leq t_5 \\ \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_6) & , t_5 \leq t \leq t_6 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The mean square value of the output current ripple over one switching period is expressed in (8). This is expanded in (9) and (10).

$$\tilde{i}_{o1}^2 = \frac{1}{T_s} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T_s} \tilde{i}_{o1}^2 dt = \frac{2}{T_s} \int_{t_0}^{t_3} \tilde{i}_{o1}^2 dt \quad (8)$$

$$\tilde{i}_{o1}^2 = \frac{2}{T_s} \left(\int_0^{T_0} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 t^2 dt + \int_0^{T_1} \left(\left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)t + \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)T_0 \right)^2 dt + \int_0^{T_2} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 t^2 dt \right) \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{i}_{o1}^2 = \frac{2}{T_s} \left(\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 T_0^3 + \\ & \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 T_1^3 + \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right) \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right) T_0 T_1^2 + \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 T_0^2 T_1 + \\ & \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 T_2^3 \end{aligned} \right) \quad (10)$$

The time intervals T_0 , T_1 and T_2 in Figure 2(a) each is represented in (11)-(13) respectively.

$$T_0 = \frac{1-v_A^r}{4} T_s \quad (11)$$

$$T_1 = \frac{v_A^r - v_B^r}{4} T_s \quad (12)$$

$$T_2 = \frac{1+v_B^r}{4} T_s \quad (13)$$

From Figure 2(b), the current ripple in the interval of $\gamma \leq \theta < \pi/2$ can be represented as (14).

$$\tilde{i}_{o2} = \frac{1}{L} \begin{cases} \left(-\frac{\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_0) & , t_0 \leq t \leq t_1 \\ \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_2) & , t_1 \leq t \leq t_3 \\ \left(-\frac{\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)(t-t_4) & , t_3 \leq t \leq t_4 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The mean square value of the output current ripple over one switching period is in (15) and expanded in (16) and (17).

$$\tilde{i}_{o2}^2 = \frac{1}{T_s} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T_s} \tilde{i}_{o2}^2 dt = \frac{2}{T_s} \int_{t_0}^{t_2} \tilde{i}_{o2}^2 dt \quad (15)$$

$$\tilde{i}_{o2}^2 = \frac{2}{T_s} \left(\int_0^{T_0} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 t^2 dt + \int_0^{T_1} \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 t^2 dt \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\tilde{i}_{o2}^2 = \frac{2}{T_s} \left(\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 T_0^3 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{E_d-\bar{v}_{AB}}{L}\right)^2 T_1^3 \right) \quad (17)$$

The time intervals T_0 and T_1 in Figure 2(b) each is represented in (18) and (19) respectively.

$$T_0 = \frac{1-v_a^r}{4} T_s \quad (18)$$

$$T_1 = \frac{1+v_a^r}{4} T_s \quad (19)$$

Finally, the current ripple mean square over a fundamental period is expressed in (20).

$$\tilde{I}_{orms}^2 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\gamma \tilde{I}_{o1}^2 d\theta + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_\gamma^{\pi/2} \tilde{I}_{o2}^2 d\theta \quad (20)$$

The result is as (21).

$$\tilde{I}_{orms}^2 = \left(\frac{E_d}{L f_s} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{96} \right) \left(\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{3 \sin(2\gamma) - 6\gamma + 4\pi}{\pi} \right) k^2 + \\ & \left(\frac{6 \cos(3\gamma) - 54 \cos(\gamma) - 16}{3\pi} \right) k^3 + \\ & \left(\frac{-3 \sin(4\gamma) + 24 \sin(2\gamma) - 36\gamma + 24\pi}{8\pi} \right) k^4 \end{aligned} \right) \quad (21)$$

Where $f_s = 1/T_s$ is the switching frequency.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

To verify the analytical result, experiments are carried out by using a capacitor start induction motor as the inverter load. The complete experimental setup is shown in Figure 3. The schematic diagram is shown in Figure 3(a) and the laboratory prototype is shown in Figure 3(b). Besides of the inverter and the induction motor, it consists of a transformer (number 1 in Figure 3(b)) to step down the voltage source from 220 V to 75 V and a three-phase rectifier with capacitor filter (number 2 in Figure 3(b)) to produce a DC voltage for the inverter. From this we get 183 Vdc power supply.

The inverter (number 3 in Figure 3(b)) is made of FGH40N60SFD 600V/40A IGBT and TLP350 optocoupler for the gate driver. The PWMs are programmed in TMS28379 digital signal processor. The switching frequencies are chosen to be not so high in order to get good precision in the ripple data. The inverter output current is sensed by using LA-55P LEM current sensor and recorded by a digital oscilloscope. Then, the recorded signal is passed to a high pass filter with a cut-off frequency of 450 Hz to get the current ripple signal. This is processed by PSIM software to produce the RMS (root mean square) of the current ripple.

Figure 3. Experimental setup (a) schematic diagram and (b) laboratory prototype

The induction motor is shown in Figure 3(b) number 4. The capacitors are used during the starting time. During the running period, these capacitors are disconnected from the inverter (Figure 4(a)). The equivalent circuit of a single-phase induction motor when running is shown in Figure 4(b). The parameters in

Figure 4(b) are the stator resistance R_s of 3.18 Ohm, the stator leakage inductance L_{ls} of 3.08 mH, the rotor resistance R_r of 2.63 Ohm, the rotor leakage inductance L_{lr} of 3.08 mH, and the magnetizing inductance L_m of 54.31 mH. The inductance L in (21) is equal to the summation of the stator leakage inductance L_{ls} and the rotor leakage inductance L_{lr} . The experiments are conducted under no-load motor operation.

Figure 4. Capacitor start induction motor: (a) circuit diagram and (b) equivalent circuit during running

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on (21), the graph of the normalized inverter output current ripples of SPWM and DPWMs for various discontinuous angle values is shown in Figure 5. In the figure, DPWM γ means discontinuous PWM with a discontinuous angle of γ . The DPWMs switching frequencies are normalized with respect to SPWM. From the graph, it can be seen that DPWM60 and DPWM75 give smaller current ripple than SPWM at high modulation index. DPWM60 produces a lower current ripple when the modulation index is more than 0.905. For DPWM75, the lower current ripple is obtained from a modulation index of more than 0.880. At a modulation index of 1.0, the DPWM60 can reduce the ripple by about 9.302% and DPWM75 reduce the ripple by about 6.312%. The DPWM45, DPWM30, and DPWM15 do not provide improvement. Because of this, it is DPWM60 and DPWM75 that will be clarified in the experiment. The DPWMs with discontinuous angles of 0° and 90° produce similar output current ripple to SPWM.

Figure 5. Inverter output current ripple as a function of modulation index

The experimental results are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7, each with a modulation index of 1.0 and a modulation index of 0.5, respectively. The switching frequencies for SPWM, DPWM75, and DPWM60 are 2750 Hz, 3000 Hz, and 3300 Hz respectively. They are chosen for similar switching numbers in each modulation type during the fundamental period. From Figure 6, we can see that DPWM60 (Figure 6(a)) gives the smallest current ripple, followed by DPWM75 (Figure 6(b)) and SPWM (Figure 6(c)). From Figure 7, we can see clearly that DPWM60 (Figure 7(a)) produces the highest current ripple, and the lowest current ripple is provided by SPWM (Figure 7(c)). DPWM75 (Figure 7(b)) gives the middle current ripple. Those experimental results are matched with the predicted results in Figure 5. The current ripple RMS as a function of the modulation index is shown in Figure 8. The figure shows that the matching of the analytical and experimental results can be appreciated. The current ripples for modulation index greater than 0.3 only are considered here. This is because, for a modulation index less than 0.3, the motor can't start successfully.

Figure 6. Inverter output current (3.33 Ampere/Div and 2.5 mS/Div) when the modulation index is 1.0: (a) DPWM60, (b) DPWM75, and (c) SPWM

Figure 7. Inverter output current (3.33 Ampere/Div and 2.5 mS/Div) when the modulation index is 0.5: (a) DPWM60, (b) DPWM75 and (c) SPWM

Figure 8. Inverter output current ripple as a function of modulation index

5. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a DPWM for a single-phase full bridge inverter. The output current ripple has been calculated analytically and compared to the experimental results. The output current ripples resulting from DPWMs with discontinuous angles of 0°, 15°, 30°, 45°, 60°, 75°, and 90° have been presented. It is known that only DPWM60 and DPWM75 give benefits when compared to SPWM. The DPWMs produce a smaller current ripple compared to SPWM at a high modulation index (more than 0.880 for DPWM75 and 0.905 for DPWM60). The experimental results show agreement with the analytical calculation. In future research, variable switching frequency will be applied to the proposed modulation in the hope of producing a lower output current ripple.

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